

Effects of Coping Strategies used by University Students in the Management of their Psychosocial Problems in the University of Buea and University of Bamenda

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ABSTRACT: Students' psychosocial problems are managed in and out of the school milieu, as a result students have been making use of some coping strategies for the management of these problems. one of these coping strategies is the use counselling services, peer support, extracurricular activities and spiritual services. The purpose of this study was to investigate the effects of coping strategies used by university students in the management of their psychosocial problems in the University of Buea and University of Bamenda. One specific objectives of this study was to assess the effects of guidance counselling services in the management of psychosocial problems amongst university students in the University of Buea and University and Bamenda. These research objectives were translated into research questions and research hypotheses. The study employed the mixed methods approach notably the sequential-explanatory design. In this perspective, instruments such as structured questionnaire and interview guides were used. A total of 488 students were validated for the final data analysis and 2 guidance counsellors, 2 student pastors and 2 student representative. Data from the questionnaires were digitalized with the support of EpiData 3.1 and descriptive and inferential statistical analyses were done with the support of SPSS version 26.0. As for the qualitative data, their abstraction was reduced through the systematic process of thematic analysis. The findings for this study show that, amongst the four indicators of the independent variable operationalized in this study, guidance counseling services ($r\text{-comp}=0.703$) are the most effective in managing psychosocial problems This therefore implies that the conceptual components significantly has an impact on university students' capacity to manage their psychosocial problems. It was recommended that, the training of school guidance counselors while in their professional schools should be given more attention, as they are very effective in the management of students' psychosocial problems.

Keywords: Coping Strategies, Psychosocial Problems and Psychosocial Health.

1. GENERAL INTRODUCTION

Background to the Study

The background to this study constitutes the historical, conceptual, theoretical and contextual. The historical background captured the historical evolution of coping strategies and psychosocial problems; the conceptual background will discuss the concepts of coping strategies and psychosocial problems. The study proceeds to consider the components of the independent variable: (guidance counselling, spiritual counselling, peer support and extracurricular activities) in relation to the dependent variable (psychosocial problems) of students, and how students can use the various coping strategies in the management od their psychosocial problems. Additionally, the theories and models relating to the study will be discussed.

Coping strategies are a series of actions, or a thought process, consciously used in the management of a stressful or unpleasant situation. They can be behavioural or cognitive strategies put in place for the management of crises. Coping strategies are used in the management of students'

psychosocial problems that enable the students to successfully complete their specific academic goals. University students often use emotional coping strategies, such as self-blame, rumination, and emotional expression, to manage stress and anxiety.

Some systematic reviews and meta-analyses showed effectiveness of the seeking of coping strategies by students in universities. The analyses showed that there were some considerable overall effects. The sustainability of these effects has also been a critical worry of some researchers and it was identified that sustainability was most pronounced for coping strategies used by students in the management of some symptoms like depression and stress. (Conley, Durlak & Kirsch, 2015)

Guidance and counselling programmes used by some students for coping was found to be essential in assisting students cope with the challenges they face while in and out of school. Some of these challenges according to Melgosa (2001) include physical and psychological changes they face due to adolescence and early adulthood. The challenges of adolescents according to Melgosa (1997) include adapting to their new image, facing the growing academic demands, establishing vocational goals, learning to control sexuality, emotional and psychological independence from their parents. (Melgosa, 2001). The rationale to offer guidance and counseling services to university students is clear. Studies in the university is a period of academic, social, personal, emotional and intellectual growth for most if not all students and also accompanied with challenges. Students learning to use the available strategies to cope with physical, emotional, social and academic difficulties will help them understand better their learning strengths and weaknesses and therefore their academic achievement can be improved and their overall development can be enhanced. In Cameroon the effects of spiritual counselling and guidance counselling in the administration and management of students has been recognized as being instrumental in the manage of unwanted behaviours amongst students which are closely related to their psychosocial health. (UNESCO, 2006)

Theoretically, from the context of behavioural research, coping strategies have often been based on whole individual. Theories such as the Health Belief Model have critically made a contribution to the theoretical evidence-base and to the understanding of why students will choose to seek for help in an attempt to cope with their psychosocial problems.

Erikson's Model of psychosocial development is a structured, time-limited analysis of developmental challenges and psychosocial problems that aims to address current psychosocial problems throughout the various stages of development. The analysis of the various stages gives and insight on how these problems can be tackled within a collaborative context where victims identify problems, set goals, develop coping strategies, and evaluate the effectiveness of those strategies. (Erikson, 1959)

Adjustment which is closely related to coping was initially a biological one and was a corner stone in Darwin's theory of evolution (1859). In Biology, the term usually employed was an adaptation. Darwin maintained that only those organisms most fitted to adapt to the hazards of the physical world survived. Biologists have continued to be concerned with the problem of biological adaptations, and much of human illness is based on transformation to the stress of life.

Contextually, Universities in the United Kingdom offer their students chances to engage in extracurricular activities which may have been a contribution to the management of psychosocial problems that has lasted for more than a century. Both educational institutions and parents are aware that the effects of extracurricular activities on students is generally positive, and that it helps them develop socially and mentally. Therefore, there is a significant number of research works that support the statement that extracurricular activities have a beneficial effect on the development of a healthy social behaviour, as well as on accomplishing better academic results. (Gallagher, Zhang, & Taylor, 2004).

Statement of the Problem

Psychosocial health encompasses the mental, emotional, social, and spiritual dimensions of what it means to be healthy. Psychosocial problems are the result of complex interaction between a person's history and his or her thoughts about and interpretations of the past and what the past

means to the individual. Studying is a great task which makes a great domain of a student's life which comes to interact with other domains which are also very important. This interaction may produce some difficulties in a student's life which greatly affect his/her studies. These difficulties are what we call psychosocial problems. As a result of these psychosocial problems, coping strategies have been used by some students which help to ameliorate circumstances surrounding their study life.

Coping strategies, have a critical place in the management of psychosocial problems. Some strategies over the years have been effective in the relieving students of the burden of their psychosocial problems. Students' awareness and perception has also been a barrier in the utilization of services that could be effective for their coping. These services have gradually become inactive because of underutilization.

There are coping strategies that should involve interaction between students, teachers, administration, guidance counsellors, chaplains and others, which normally should be effective in the management psychosocial problems. Some of these strategies are favourable for the reduction of psychosocial problems but are not implemented optimally amongst the above-mentioned group of people which has increased the occurrence of psychosocial problems amongst university students. Gaps may exist at the availability of these services students use for coping strategies, also at the utilisation of these services put in place for intervention and lastly at level of the sustainability of the effects of these strategies. This study will identify the effectiveness of coping strategies used by students regarding psychosocial problems.

Research Objectives

General Objective

To assess the effects of coping strategies used by university students in Cameroon in the management of their psychosocial problems?

Specific Objective

To Assess the effects of guidance counselling services in the management of psychosocial problems amongst university students in Cameroon

Research Question

General Research Question

What are the effects of coping strategies used by university students in Cameroon in the management of their psychosocial problems?

Specific Research Question

What are the effects of guidance counselling services in the management of psychosocial problems

Research Hypotheses

General Hypothesis

H₀: Student's coping strategies are not effective in the management of their psychosocial problems.

H_a: coping strategies are effective in the management of their psychosocial problems.

Specific Hypothesis

H₀₁: Guidance Counselling services are not effective in the management of psychosocial problems amongst university students in Cameroon

H_{a1}: Guidance Counselling services are effective in the management of psychosocial problems amongst university students in Cameroon

Justification of the Study

This study is to identify coping strategies used by students in the management of their psychosocial problems. How these policies either favour the reduction of these problems or does not take them into consideration which has led to an increase in psychosocial problems and may have an effect on their educational outcomes.

This work will show the extent to which students use coping strategies through peer support, counselling services, spiritual services and extracurricular activities. This study highlights the needs to take a new look at the use of coping strategies by students in universities by conceptualizing it as an aspect interacting with other variables. Little is known relatively about how these services are used by students promote or hinder thriving in general and resilience in particular. The concerns on the effects of psychosocial well-being on secondary school students' environmental adjustment and in the society at large are critical. The inability to take the concerns as such by educational stakeholders' affects secondary school students and the society psychologically, socially, emotionally, economically and physically (Amani, 2010). Additionally, this problem is worth investigating because little or no research specifically on psychosocial well-being and effects on secondary school students' environmental adjustment have been, as revealed by literature.

Significance of the Study

This study will be significant to universities, teachers, students and families. University administrators and authorities will get to know how strategies they have put in place for their students are appropriate enough for the management of student psychosocial health problems and other mental health challenges. Particularly, the university will be able to assess the effectiveness of the services chosen for this study to a particular extent from the results of this study. Some administrative and academic aspects that contribute to students' psychosocial problems will be closely identified and taken into consideration by both administrative and teaching staff.

This study will be very important for teachers as they act very much and students' mentors and coaches also, as their peers. This will help to create awareness amongst staff that students face challenges in their lives generally and even in their education. This will help teachers create more supportive and collaborative environments for their students. This will improve teachers' collaboration with students on how to handle their various challenges.

Operational Definition of Terms

Psychosocial health

This refers to the development of cognitive, emotional, and spiritual strengths among individuals, families and communities which creates overall positive social relationships among them (East African Community, 2019).

Huppert (2009) defined psychosocial well-being as feeling good and functioning effectively. It refers to how people evaluate their lives. These evaluations may be in the form of cognitions or in the form of affect. The cognitive part is an information-based appraisal of one's life that is when a person gives conscious evaluative judgments about one's satisfaction with life as a whole. The affective part is a hedonic evaluation guided by emotions and feelings such as frequency with which people experience pleasant/unpleasant 97 moods in reaction to their lives. The assumption behind this is that most people evaluate their life as either good or bad, so they are normally able to offer judgments.

In the context of this study psychosocial well-being emphasizes the right of all students to have a happy life "here and now", with a "development approach", which underscores the importance of students developing the skills to improve their well-being in the present and in the future (Ben-Arieh et al., 2013).

Psychosocial Problems

Psychosocial problems include the broad spectrum of various complaints which may not be strictly medical or somatic. They affect the students functioning in daily life, his or her education, environment and/or life events. As young adults, students find themselves having serious financial problems, development of toxic relationships, and for some, early parenthood, pursuit of greater educational opportunities, cross-cultural issues, family problems, academic frustration, drugs and alcohol consumption, poor interpersonal attachments academic overload, constant pressure to succeed, competition with peers, concerns about the future academic unreadiness, poor study habits and employment prospects which all contribute to the development of psychosocial crisis (Mikolajczyk, Brzoska, Maier, Ottova, Meier et al., 2008) (Kitzrow, 2003); (Tosevski, Milovancevic, & Gajic, 2010).

Coping

Coping is defined as coping with the problems of normal, everyday life (Halonen & Santrock, 1997; Weiten, Dunn & Hammer, 2015), which involves the degree to which an individual engages in competent social behaviour and adapts to the immediate social context (Crick and Dodge, 1994).

Adjustment here is the process in which an individual balance the needs and the circumstances that affects the fulfilment of these needs. Successful balancing leads to success in adjustment, finding meaning and purpose, and learning the necessary skills that enables an individual to engage in competent social behaviour and adapts to the immediate social context (Crick & Dodge, 1994).

Coping refers to the continuous process in which a person varies his behaviour to produce a more harmonious relationship between himself and his environment (Malami, 2017). It's also, refers to a student's interaction with his or her environment that fosters the acquisition of may be physical or behavioural competencies, which will help the student to survive better in the environment (Joe et al. 2020 and Abdullah, Elias, Mahyuddin & Uli, 2009).

Environmental adjustment here equally, is a method that changes the demands from the environment according to the capacities of an individual so that the individual's psychosocial aspects are not burdened (Shoko and Masayoshi, 2021). Additionally, here environmental adjustment means, to fit, make suitable, adapt, arrange, modify, harmonize or make correspondent. In some situation, one of the factors may not be changeable and so the one which is, has to be modified in some way to suit the other. Also, adjusting to an environment means adapting to the conditions and demands of a particular situation or setting. Equally, it is the adjustment of organisms to their environment in order to improve their chances at survival in that environment. This can involve changes in behaviour, physical characteristics, or other traits to better fit the environment (Joe and chris et al., 2011).

Rogers (1952) describes counselling as the process by which the structure of the self is relaxed in the safety of the clients' relationship with the therapist and previously desired experiences are perceived and then integrated into an altered self". Pepisky and Pepisky (1954) defined counselling as that interaction which occurs between two individuals called counsellor and client, and takes place in a professional setting and is initiated and maintained to facilitate changes in the behaviour of a client".

In this study, Counselling is a learning oriented process carried in a simple one to one social environment in which the counsellor, professionally competent in relevant psychosocial skills and knowledge seeks to assist the students by methods appropriate to the student's needs and within the context of the total personnel programme, to learn how to put such understanding into effect in relation to more clearly perceived, realistically defined goals to the end that the student may become a happier and more productive member of society.

Coping Strategy

Coping strategies are a series of actions, or a thought process, consciously used in the management of a stressful or unpleasant situation. They can be behavioural or cognitive strategies put in place for the management of crises. Coping strategies are used in the management of students' psychosocial problems that enable the students to successfully complete their specific academic goals. University students often use emotional coping strategies, such as self-blame, rumination, and emotional expression, to manage stress and anxiety. In daily academic life, students are exposed to a wide range of potentially stressful situations which make up their psychosocial problems which could negatively affect their academic achievement and their health. Among the factors that could be weakened by academic stress, attention has been paid to expectations of self-efficacy, which are considered one of the most important determinants for student engagement, persistence, and academic success. From a proactive perspective, research on academic stress has emphasized the importance of coping strategies in preventing harmful consequences. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in discovering the extent to which individuals are able to combine different coping strategies and the adaptive consequences this flexibility entails. (Kashdan & Ciarrochi, 2013).

Peer Support

Peer support occurs when people provide knowledge, experience, emotional, social or practical help to each other. It commonly refers to an initiative consisting of trained supporters (although it can be provided by peers without training), and can take a number of forms such as peer mentoring, reflective listening (reflecting content and/or feelings), or counseling. Peer support is also used to refer to initiatives where colleagues, members of self-help organizations and others meet, in person or online, as equals to give each other connection and support on a reciprocal basis. Peer support is distinct from other forms of social support in that the source of support is a *peer*, a person who is similar in fundamental ways to the recipient of the support; their relationship is one of equality. A peer is in a position to offer support by virtue of relevant experience: he or she has "been there, done that" and can relate to others who are now in a similar situation. Trained peer support workers such as peer support specialists and peer counselors receive special training and are required to obtain Continuing Education Units, like clinical staff. Some other trained peer support workers may also be law-enforcement personnel and firefighters as well as emergency medical responders. The social peer support also offers an online system of distributed expertise, interactivity, social distance and control, which may promote disclosure of personal problems (Paterson, Brewer, & Leeseberg, 2013).

Counseling Services in Universities

The aims of the guidance and counseling service are similar to the purposes of education in general—to assist the student in fulfilling her basic physiological needs, understanding herself and acceptance of others, developing associations with peers, balancing between permissiveness and controls in the educational setting, realizing successful achievement, and providing opportunities to gain independence (Heyden, 2011). The purposes of guidance and counseling provide emphasis and strength to the educational program. Despite its growing importance, however, there is currently no comprehensive global overview of psychological counseling among universities. To the best of our knowledge, only a few systematic review studies analyzed specific aspects of this macro-topic, focusing on digital mental health interventions, the effectiveness of mobile app-based psychological interventions and the use of mental health services among university students. The first review included 88 articles and found that digital mental health interventions can be effective for improving depression, anxiety, and psychological well-being among college students. The second review included only 19 articles and showed that mobile apps for mental health intervention exist and demonstrate good acceptability and feasibility, demonstrating efficacy among students. The third review synthesized, both qualitatively and quantitatively, evidence from 44 studies analyzing the proportion of university students using mental health services, and how this varies by service type. They found a large variety of available services used by varying proportions of students.

However, the included studies were mostly conducted in the USA, limiting the generalizability of their results. (McLeod, S. 2018).

Extracurricular Activities in Universities

An extracurricular activity (ECA) or extra academic activity (EAA) or cultural activities is an activity, performed by students, that falls outside the realm of the normal curriculum of school, college or university education. Such activities are generally voluntary (as opposed to mandatory), social, philanthropic, and often involve others of the same age. Students and staff direct these activities under faculty sponsorship, although student-led initiatives, such as independent newspapers, are very common. However, sometimes the school principals and teachers also bring in these activities in the school among the students' Extra-curricular activities simply mean things that you do outside of your normal school routine that compliments your school studies, develop your skills and crucially show admissions officers that they should choose you to study at their university. Now, this doesn't have to mean that you do these outsides of school, many top schools will offer classes like this as standard (Bassler, 2020).

Spiritual Counselling

Spiritual Care may include: Supporting you in exploring your feelings and emotions, Leading guided meditations or breathing exercises, Actively listening to your thoughts and questions, Providing a compassionate and caring presence, Helping you identify and live into your values, Creating rituals to honor milestones, Supporting your religious needs and Offering prayers or blessings. (Kheswa J., & Mahlalda 2014).

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Introduction

Literature review means the works the researcher consulted in order to understand and investigate the research problem. It is an account of what has been published on a topic by accredited scholars and researchers (Kombo and Tromp, 2006). Therefore, literature review is the critical examination of various readings such as books, newspapers, magazines, journals, encyclopaedias and dissertations, among other written sources, then incorporating relevant issues in the study being conducted. This chapter deals with the review of literature related to the phenomenon under investigation. The literature review was organized, under the following sections; conceptual review, theoretical review and empirical review.

Conceptual Review

The conceptual review will be organized under the following themes; psychosocial problems, coping strategies, effects of coping strategies, school-based extracurricular activities, peer support. This section will help bring out the relationship between the various concepts stated above and how they bring more understanding to the subject matter.

Psychosocial Problems

Around the world, students in higher education suffer from and deal with psychosocial problems. This phenomenon is universal and seems to be increasing. A vast number of students enter higher education with problems like stress, anxiety or depression, or develop them during their student lives, due to, for example, loneliness, family crisis, mental health or study environment issues. (Ovuga et al., 2006).

Psychosocial Problems Amongst University Students

Problems in Understanding Academic Concepts

Acquiring an efficient understanding of the academic concepts is regarded as one of the major objectives of students in achieving academic goals. When they experience problems in acquiring an understanding of academic concepts, they encounter barriers in completion of assignments, projects, achieve low grades in tests and exams and experience setbacks in enhancing their academic

performance. When students experience problems in understanding academic concepts, they feel stressed and anxious. But, when they inculcate the traits of diligence, resourcefulness and conscientiousness, they are able to provide solutions to their academic problems. (Anwar & Rana, 2023). The students need to form good terms and relationships with individuals within their educational institutions, particularly, educators and fellow students. Maintaining good terms and relationships and development of effective communication skills will help in providing solutions to various problems and challenges and in rendering a good academic performance. Furthermore, students, primarily in schools discuss with their parents regarding their problems and they make an attempt to provide them support and assistance. These are usually, technologies, learning materials, private coaching classes and so forth. (Norman & Seggane, 2014)

As class sizes in education are increasing and technology is impacting on education at all levels, these trends create significant challenges for teachers as they attempt to support individual students. Technology undoubtedly provides substantial advantages for students, enabling them to access information from around the planet easily and at any time. (Ahmad, 2005). The advantages and disadvantages of the increased use of technology have come to light over time as students increasingly engage with new innovations. In this review, we will address an issue that has become progressively evident in digital learning environments but is relevant to all educational settings, particularly as class sizes grow. We will explore the difficulties in attempting to understand and account for the struggles students experience while learning a particular emphasis on what happens when students experience difficulties and become confused. (Best & Kahn, 2006).

Running into problems while learning is often accompanied by an emotional response. Emotion, more broadly, plays a vital role in the integration of new knowledge with prior knowledge. This has been found to be the case in brain imaging studies, laboratory-based studies, and applied educational studies. A clear example of how emotion can impact on the learning process is where it creates an obstacle to learning, reflected in, for example, the vast body of work that has examined the detrimental effect of anxiety on the learning of mathematics. Similarly, confusion has been associated with blockages or impasses in the learning process. (Cooper & Schindler, 2011).

Despite its importance, understanding, identifying and responding to difficulties and the resulting emotions in learning can be problematic, particularly in larger classes and in digital environments. Without the affordances of synchronous face-to-face human interaction in digital environments, emotions like confusion are difficult to detect. (Creswell, J.W. 2009). It is therefore challenging to respond to students with support or feedback to help their progress when they are stuck and become confused. Humans are uniquely tuned to respond to the emotional reactions of other humans. (Ekwonye, 2020) Intuitively we know what it is like to feel confused as a result of a difficulty in the learning process, yet confusion is not regarded as one of the “basic” emotions: like, for example, happiness, sadness, and anger. And while student confusion is relatively easy for an experienced teacher to detect in face-to-face settings, it is a complex emotion that is difficult to explain scientifically. But we know that confusion is both commonly felt by students, is able to be diagnosed by teachers, and able to be resolved productively with teacher support (see for example. Thus, at the most fundamental level, confusion is both widely experienced and relatively easily detected by teachers, despite the uncertainty about the exact relationship between difficulties and emotional responses in learning. (Frieese & Koenig, 1993).

Thus, student emotions, such as confusion, are relatively straightforward for experienced teachers to detect, understand and respond to in face-to-face settings with relatively small class sizes. The same is not true in digital environments or large classes. Emotions are less obvious to teachers when there are many students or when they interact with students via electronic methods. This means that alternate practices are needed to respond to students when they experience difficulties in these emerging environments. (Frost, 2019). The increased difficulty in detecting and responding to student emotions is one of several key reasons why a deeper understanding of difficulties and associated emotional responses is needed as new technologies and increasing class sizes impact education. Digital learning environments, especially online or distance learning environments, are often explicitly designed so that students will have flexibility and autonomy in their studies.

Students, when studying online or at a distance, are often able to access course material and resources in their own time (and place) and are often not constrained by centralized timetables. (Hall GS. 2015) As a result, there is often a greater onus on students in these environments to be more autonomous and self-directed in their learning. Thus, increased learning flexibility often leads to students having fewer opportunities for engaging with teaching staff and receiving feedback in real time. While activities can be made available in the form of webinars and other synchronous formats, there remains a substantial responsibility on students to be autonomous and make good decisions about their own progress without requiring the real-time intervention of teaching staff. (Hira, 2014)

Counseling Services in Universities

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Until now, no study has tried to give an overview of the situation of counseling worldwide. This review was designed and conducted to that end. Specifically, we aimed to review articles addressing: (a) attitudes regarding help-seeking behaviors or counseling services among university students or counselors, (b) mental health among university students who are accessing or attending counseling services, (c) the effectiveness of psychological counseling/interventions among university students, and (d) the description of protocols/good practices/purposes or counseling services among student communities and universities. (Yusof, 2017). Through an examination of the geographical distribution, actuality, and typology of contributions, as well as the methodological quality and robustness of studies currently published in the existing literature, this review aims to provide insight into the functioning of UCSs, identify gaps and limitations, and highlight areas for future research. Namely, this review can shed light on the attitudes, barriers, and stereotypes concerning health-seeking behaviors, the mental health of university students who utilize UCSs, and the effectiveness of psychological interventions in this population. By outlining the protocols, good practices, and purposes of UCSs, this review can also help identify strategies to enhance the support offered to university students, particularly in light of the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, which has had a well-established, profound impact on their mental health. (Cui, et al., 2010).

Higher education represents the final stage of formal education, where the learning process differs significantly from secondary schools. Responsibility for learning is predominantly placed on students, as instructors or professors merely provide foundational knowledge, and students are expected to engage in independent learning. At the stage of higher education, individuals are in their late adolescence and early adulthood, where they are expected to become independent, responsible, and capable of developing social roles within a society with diverse values. However, if students are unaware of the forms of learning and the demands placed on them, they may

encounter various problems within themselves and conflicts with their surroundings. Without assistance in resolving these issues, students may experience failures in their lives. Furthermore, psychological development is not only experienced by individuals currently studying in school but also by adults and even the elderly in their families, community, or workplace (Salzer, 2002).

"Guidance and counseling programs and services are needed not only in schools but also in the community and work environments, tailored to the characteristics of the individuals being guided and the different problems they face." Hence, higher education institutions, as providers of quality human resources specializing in guidance and counseling, have specific classifications to prepare individuals who will serve as experts in the field of guidance and counseling in both educational and professional settings. This ensures that graduates can cope with the changes that occur and help address emerging problems (Laurie, 2010).

Therefore, guidance and counseling services play a crucial role, as every individual faces

challenges in their lives that require prompt intervention and problem-solving. If left unresolved, these challenges can hinder a student's progress and lead to failure (Sukmawati, 2011). Some specific aims of the school guidance and counseling program include the following (Gibson, 2009).

To Provide for the Realization of Student Potentialities

To all students, the school offers a wide choice of courses and co-curricular activities. A significant function of education is to help students identify and develop their potentialities. The counselor's role is to assist students to distribute their energies into the many learning opportunities available to them. Every student needs help in planning his major course of study and pattern of co-curricular activities. (Gajic, 2010).

To Help Children with Developing Problems

Even those students who have chosen an appropriate educational program for themselves may have problems that require help. A teacher may need to spend from one-fifth to one-third of his time with a few pupils who require a great deal of help, which deprives the rest of the class from the teacher's full attention to their needs. The counselor, by helping these youngsters to resolve their difficulties, frees the classroom teacher to use his time more efficiently. (UNESCO, 2006).

To Contribute to the Development of the School's Curriculum

Counselors, in working with individual students, know their personal problems and aspirations, their talents and abilities, as well as the social pressures confronting them. Counselors, therefore, can provide data that serve as a basis for curriculum development, and they can help curriculum developers shape courses of study that more accurately reflect the needs of students. Too often, counselors are not included in curriculum development efforts. (Ramirez et al. 2023).

To Provide Teachers with Technical Assistance

Pre-service teacher training institutions typically provide very limited experience with the more technical aspects of guidance work. Thus, a need exists in most schools for assistance with guidance and counseling functions essential to the educational program. Specifically, the guidance counselor is qualified to assist teachers with selecting, administering, and interpreting tests; selecting and using cumulative, anecdotal, and other types of records; providing help and suggestions relative to counseling techniques, which teachers can use in counseling their students; and providing leadership in developing and conducting professional development of teachers in guidance functions. (Oteng-Abayie, 2017).

To Contribute to the Mutual Adjustment of Students and the School

Guidance has a responsibility for developing and maintaining a cooperative relationship between students and the school. Teachers and counselors must be cognizant of students' needs. Students also must make adjustments to the school. They have a responsibility to contribute something to the school. A major contribution of students is that of making appropriate use of the school's resources and working toward accomplishments. Such mutual adjustment of students and school is facilitated

by providing suggestions for program improvements, conducting research for educational improvements, contributing to students' adjustment through counseling, and fostering wholesome school-home attitudes (Davidson, 2017).

The Role of the Counselor

The major goals of counseling are to promote personal growth and to prepare students to become motivated workers and responsible citizens. Educators recognize that in addition to intellectual challenges, students encounter personal/social, educational, and career challenges. School guidance and counseling programs need to address these challenges and to promote educational success. The guidance and counseling program is an integral part of a school's total educational program; it is developmental by design, focusing on needs, interests, and issues related to various stages of student growth. The scope of the developmental guidance and counseling program in today's school include the following components (Cooley, 2010; Coy, 2004).

- Personal/social - In addition to providing guidance services for all students, counselors are expected to do personal and crisis counseling. Problems such as dropping out, substance abuse, suicide, irresponsible sexual behavior, eating disorders, and pregnancy must be addressed.
- Educational - Students must develop skills that will assist them as they learn. The counselor, through classroom guidance activities and individual and group counseling, can assist students in applying effective study skills, setting goals, learning effectively, and gaining test-taking skills. Counselors also may focus on note taking, time management, memory techniques, relaxation techniques, overcoming test anxiety, and developing listening skills. (Hadulla, 2015).
- Career - Planning for the future, combating career stereotyping, and analyzing skills and interests are some of the goals students must develop in school. Career information must be available to students, and representatives from business and industry must work closely with the school and the counselor in preparing students for the world of work. (Stuenkel, 1992).

Major Guidance and Counseling Services

The primary mission of a school's guidance and counseling program is to provide a broad spectrum of personnel services to the students. These services include student assessment, the information service, placement and follow-up, and counseling assistance. These four areas should constitute the core of any guidance program and should be organized to facilitate the growth and development of all students from kindergarten through post high school experiences (Erford, 2010; Erford, 2011; Neukrug, 2011).

Assessment

The assessment service is designed to collect, analyze, and use a variety of objective and subjective personal, psychological, and social data about each pupil. Its purpose is to help the individual to better understand herself. Conferences with pupils and parents, standardized test scores, academic records, anecdotal records, personal data forms, case studies, and portfolios are included. The school counselor interprets this information to pupils, parents, teachers, administrators, and other professionals. Pupils with special needs and abilities are thus identified. (Durlak, 2017).

Information

The information service is designed to provide accurate and current information in order that the students may make an intelligent choice of an educational program, an occupation, or a social activity. Essentially, the aim is that with such information students will make better choices and will engage in better planning in and out of the school setting. Students must not only be exposed to such information but must also have an opportunity to react to it in a meaningful way with others. (Kirsch, 2015).

Placement and Follow-up

The school assists the student in selecting and utilizing opportunities within the school and in the outside labor market. Counselors assist students in making appropriate choices of courses of study

and in making transitions from one school level to another, one school to another, and from school to employment. Placement thereby involves pupil assessment, informational services, and counseling assistance appropriate to the pupil's choices of school subjects, co-curricular activities, and employment. Follow-up is concerned with the development of a systematic plan for maintaining contact with former students. The data obtained from the follow-up studies aid the school in evaluating the school's curricular and guidance programs. (Creswell, 2009).

Counseling

The counseling service is designed to facilitate self-understanding and development through dyadic or small-group relationships. The aim of such relationships tends to be on personal development and decision making that is based on self- understanding and knowledge of the environment. The counselor assists the student to understand and accept himself thereby clarifying his ideas, perceptions, attitudes, and goals; furnishes personal and environmental information to the pupil, as required, regarding his plans, choices, or problems; and seeks to develop in the student the ability to cope with/and solve problems and increased competence in making decisions and plans for the future. Counseling is generally accepted as the heart of the guidance service. (Karyotaki, 2021).

Theoretical Review

At the theoretical review, theories relevant to the concepts under investigation will be reviewed. These theories here include: Theoretically, the Health Belief Model so that the theory can be tested and a contribution made to the theoretical evidence-base. However, in school settings there is a need for interventions that address these problems to improve psychosocial health outcomes, without needing to adhere to rigid theoretical frameworks. Consequently, new methods have been developed which take the behavioural problem as a starting point and use insights from different theories to assess, solve or prevent that problem. Secondly, the Cognitive behavioural Model is a structured, time-limited approach to psychosocial problems that aims to address current psychosocial problems It uses problem-focused cognitive and behavioural strategies guided by empirical science and derived from theories of learning and cognition. These interventions are delivered within a collaborative context where therapists and clients work together to identify problems, set goals, develop intervention strategies, and evaluate the effectiveness of those strategies. Behaviour-Constraint Theory by Brehm's (1966), Adaptation- Level Theory by Harry Helson (1898-1977), Schlosberg's Transition Theory by Nancy K. Schlosberg, (1981); Person Centred Theory by Carl Rogers (1902-1987); Martin Seligman's PERMA Model (2002); Self-Determination Theory by Ryan and Deci, (2000). The reasons for choosing these theories stem from the fact that there are humanistic in nature and all the views of the theorist hint on psychosocial well-being and mental health adjustment which are the core concepts of the study.

Psychosocial Development Theory by Erik Erikson

Psychosocial development theory is an expansion of Sigmund Freud's original five stages of development. Erikson, a 20th-century psychologist and psychoanalyst, formulated the eight-stage life cycle theory in 1959 on the supposition that the environment plays a critical role in self-awareness, adjustment, human development and identity.

Erik Erikson's 8 stages of psychosocial development

Erikson asserts in his psychosocial theory that ego identity is reached by facing goals and challenges throughout eight stages of development over the entire life cycle. Each of the psychosocial stages is distinguished by two opposing emotional forces, known as contrary dispositions, that result in a crisis that needs to be resolved. Each crisis must be mastered as swiftly as possible, otherwise, a person's psychology is in jeopardy. However, a successful resolution of the conflict results in a healthy personality and the attainment of a basic virtue. The ego uses these character strengths to resolve subsequent crises. (Erikson, 1959)

1. Trust vs. Mistrust

The first stage of Erikson's psychosocial development starts at birth and continues to approximately 18 months of age. The principal task is trust versus mistrust. Infants rely solely upon their caregivers; thus, if caregivers are responsive and sensitive to their infant's needs, it helps the infant develop a sense of trust. Apathetic caregivers who do not meet their baby's needs may cause the baby to develop feelings of anxiety, fear and mistrust and see the world as unpredictable. Basic virtue developed: hope.

2. Autonomy vs. Shame and Doubt

The second stage occurs between the ages of 1½ and 3 years. If a child is allowed to develop at their own pace during this stage, they can acquire self-reliance and self-confidence. However, if parents are inconsistent, overcritical, or overprotective, the child may doubt their ability to control themselves and their world. Basic virtue developed: will.

3. Initiative vs. Guilt

The third of Erikson's eight stages of psychosocial development arises during the preschool stage, 3-5 years of age. A child can develop initiative through social interactions, and by planning and commencing in play and other activities. If the child's pursuits fail or are criticized, feelings of self-doubt and guilt may arise. Basic virtue developed: purpose.

4. Industry vs. Inferiority

The fourth stage occurs from ages 5 to 12 years. During this period, a child begins to compare themselves with peers. The child learns to be productive and to accept the evaluation of his or her efforts, and in turn, can develop a sense of accomplishment and pride in their academic work, sports, social activities and home life. If a child feels they do not measure up, feelings of inferiority or incompetence may be established. Basic virtue developed: competency.

5. Identity vs. Role Confusion

The fifth stage of psychosocial development is marked by an adolescent identity crisis. Between the ages of 12-18, an individual develops a sense of self by experimenting with a variety of social roles. An adolescent who is successful at forming a cohesive, positive identity will have a strong sense of identity, whereas adolescents who do not search for an identity or are pressured into an identity may experience role confusion and develop a weak sense of self. Basic virtue developed: fidelity.

6. Intimacy vs. Isolation

The sixth stage extends from late adolescence to early middle age, 18 to 40. A strong sense of self must be developed in adolescence in order to create intimate relationships with others during this stage. Adults who lack a positive self-concept may experience emotional isolation or loneliness.

To avoid feeling isolated or alone, individuals must learn to not lose themselves when sharing or caring for others. Gaining a strong self-identity allows an individual to achieve true intimacy, whereas identity diffusion can be a challenge. Basic virtue developed: love.

7. Generativity vs. Stagnation

Also called generativity versus self-absorption, the seventh stage in Erikson's psychosocial development theory occurs during the ages of 40-65. During middle adulthood, individuals have a positive goal of generativity. In most cases, this results in procreation, along with the fulfillment of parental and social responsibilities. This is in strict contrast to interest in the self or self-absorption. Basic virtue developed: care.

8. Integrity vs. Despair

The final stage of psychosocial development theory during old age (65+) is a period when a person reflects on life. One can either develop a sense of satisfaction with their life and approach death with peace or develop a sense of despair over missed opportunities and wasted time, leaving the individual to approach death with dread. Basic virtue developed: wisdom. (Erikson, 1959)

Assumptions of Psychosocial Development Theory

Although Erikson built his psychosocial development theory upon many years of field research and study, the theory maintains a foundation in a few assumptions. Social expectations in each stage are the same across all cultures. Parental influence exists throughout the stages of childhood and adolescence. Humans develop similarly across the eight stages.

Applications of Psychosocial Development Theory

The psychosocial development theory holds that individuals are shaped by and react to their environment. For this reason, the theory may prove to be a useful tool in many fields, including social work.

Psychosocial development theory can be utilized in the analysis of a client's symptomatic behavior in relation to past traumatic experiences and conflicts with current developmental tasks.

Social workers can use Erikson's "maturation timetable" to identify individual challenges and to determine what support and services would be best for addressing the challenges. (Erikson, 1959)

Application of the Psychosocial Development Theory in Understanding Psychosocial Problems

Erikson's theory postulates that people advance through the stages of development based on how they adjust to social crises throughout their lives. These social crises instruct how individuals react to the surrounding world. This provides social work professionals with a group of signals that help determine how successfully clients handle crises and progress along with a "maturation timetable."

The eight stages in Erikson's psychosocial development theory provide a stepping-stone for movement toward proper growth that social workers can apply to distinguish individual difficulties and, in turn, provide the appropriate support and services for tackling these challenges. (Erikson, 1959)

Empirical Review

The Effects of Guidance Counseling Services in the Management of Psychosocial Problems

The Reaching Out Survey (Karwig et al., 2015) indicated that student counselling services were the most-cited college support service previously used by students in Ireland to obtain information and support for mental health (72%) and indicated that 63% of students were likely to use this service should they need mental health support in the future. A number of university-level institutions in Ireland have reported that student retention and progression are fostered by attending student counselling services, in addition to improving their mental health and well-being, and that students value these services (Trinity College Dublin [TCD], 2018; University College Cork [UCC], 2017). The Psychological Counsellors in Higher Education Ireland (PCHEI) 2014–2015 report showed that 27% of clients (1,427) across six university-level counselling services in Ireland reported that counselling was a factor in their retention and/or progression, and 23% (1,186) reported that it helped them with their academic performance (Union of Students Ireland (USI), 2018).

Demands for student counselling services continue to rise globally (Auerbach et al., 2018; Royal College of Psychiatrists, 2011). Research conducted in the UK reported that higher education counsellors experience challenges in managing their increasing workload, dealing with the increasing intensity and severity of disturbance among students, communicating with the public health services and referring students with complex mental health difficulties to other services (Randall & Bewick, 2016; Hewitt & Wheeler, 2004). Irish universities have reported that the number of students utilising their counselling services has increased significantly over the past number of years (annual reports: Dublin City University [DCU], 2017; UCC, 2017; TCD, 2018; National University of Ireland Galway [NUIG], 2018). One report showed a 13% increase in the number of students availing of counselling services and a 20% increase in the number of counselling sessions provided in that academic year, compared with the previous year (NUIG, 2018).

In a study carried out in the USA on the effectiveness of physical environment on counselling, Pressly and Heesacker (2001) identified that common architectural characteristic of space including accessories, color, furniture, and room design, lighting, smell, sound, texture, and thermal conditions affect counselling outcomes in the healing process during counselling.

A study carried out in Australia by Sanders and Lehmann (2018) stressed the importance of modelling counselling rooms to enhance an interplay between physical and spatial features such as paint colors, natural lighting, seat positioning, temperature, and clients' thoughts and feelings. These physical-spatial features have contributed to the healing process during counselling.

Carpman and Grant (2016) affirm that clients' design-related needs are essential in enhancing the psycho-social, emotional and physical needs of clients. They suggest that accessories in a counselling room such as plants and objects like sculptures provide mental stimulation to clients, making the counselling room comfortable and appealing to counsellors, thereby revealing a counsellor's character and personality. A room facility where clients visit.

In a study done in China, Liu, Ji, Chen, and Ye (2014) found that colors in a counselling room have spectrum effectiveness that triggers physiological processes in both the counsellor and the client to particular colors. For instance, light has been known to determine a client's perception of color, texture, and form (Ching, 2015). Furniture and room design, especially positioning of furniture in a counselling room and the distance between furniture, create mutual understanding between the counsellor and the clients, bearing in mind their gender (Pressly and Heesacker, 2001). Therefore, although not directly influencing the counselling outcome, they are crucial for creating a conducive environment for counselling. As highlighted in the opening paragraph, these are aspects of counselling that are least reflected upon. This study sought to establish the status of facilities from which counseling services was undertaken.

Lighting in a counselling room affects a client's perception of his awareness of aspects of space, such as physical and emotional (Mirjam et al., 2017). Lighting also affects a counsellor's productivity in that a counsellor will have a positive perception during counselling and will have less boredom when lighting is adequate in a room (Liu et al., 2014). Therefore, counselling is likely to be more successful if a counselling room has soft lighting or natural lighting. For example, (Erlichman and Carpman and Grant 2016) found that unpleasant smell and sounds trigger unhappy memories among clients while pleasant smells and sounds in a counselling room enhance healing.

Additionally, Pressley and Heesacker (2001) found that unpleasant odours such as bad breath and an intense perfume make clients and counsellors negatively evaluate each other unconsciously during the counseling process. Therefore, smells in a counselling room determine automatically how the counsellor and client assess each other. These are overshadowed factors, yet they contribute to the outcome of counselling. This study sought to establish the status of facilities from which counseling services was undertaken. Designing a counselling room, calls for considerations on the quality and dimensions of sound because they affect counselling. Sanders and Lehmann (2018) found that slow and quiet music, such as water sounds, can actively calm emotional clients. Additionally, effectiveness counselling can thus be influenced by the type of sound in the counselling room as these sounds may keep external noises from interfering with the counselling process. Textures like walls, ceilings, floors, furniture, soft or hard surfaces create illusionary or real emotions that evoke past memories through associations (Ching, 2015). Soft texture in counselling room absorbs sound and boosts feelings of privacy in clients. However, there is limited empirical data to explain whether these aspects are considered crucial in university counseling. The above mentioned was a gap that this study sought to address. (Pressely & Heesacker, 2001).

Arguably, all these factors are essential in facilitating counselling. The Common Factors Theory underscores the importance of context in effecting desired counselling outcomes. Thus, the context is a moderating factor that communicates to both counsellors and clients the importance of counselling services in restoring psychological well-being, which plays a crucial role in academic performance and retention rate. The literature reviewed herein has demonstrated scarcity in counselling services researches in Kenyan universities and how it affects students' academic

performance and retention. This study, therefore, endeavored to investigate the status of counselling services in enhancing academic performance and retention rates in universities. (Heesacker, 2001).

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Introduction

This chapter presents the methodology that used in carrying out the study. It comprises the research design, description of the study area (Cameroon), the population of the study, target population of the study, accessible population of the study, the sample size and sampling techniques, the instruments for data collection, validity of the instruments, reliability of the instruments, method of data collection, techniques of data analysis, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

Creswell (2009) holds that a research design functions as the research blue print for measurement and analysis of data. Furthermore, Cooper and Schindler (2011) defined a research design as a plan that describes the processes data gathering, describing of phenomenon and organizing the data, in order to help the reader understand the distribution of data. Study design is the overall plan for addressing a research question, including strategies for enhancing the study's integrity (Polit & Beck 2010). This study will employ a sequential explanatory mixed method which will include collection and analysis of quantitative data followed by a collection and analysis of qualitative data. To use qualitative results to assist in explaining and interpreting the findings of a quantitative study.

Area of the Study

Generally, there are eleven state Universities in Cameroon with the oldest University of Yaoundé I and the newest (University of Ebolowa, Bertoua and Garoua which were created following the presidential decree in 2023. Cameroon is a country of over 30 million inhabitants with each region having a State University. In addition to State owned universities, there are hundreds of Private Universities own by individuals and mission/ organisation. However, despite the very brief overview of the number of State universities in Cameroon, this study was delimited or carried out in four of the State Universities of Cameroon: University of Buea, (Found in the Southwest Region) Douala, (Located in the Littoral Region), Dchang (Located in the West Region) and Bamenda (Found in the Northwest Region).

Specifically, the University of Bamenda is found in the North West Region and the campus of the University of Bamenda is located in Bambili, Tubah Sub-Division in Mezam Division of the Region. The University of Buea in the South West Region of Cameroon is in the Buea Municipality in the Fako Division in the Region. The university of Dschang in the Wourri division. In recent times, education has become one of the major activities in Buea, Douala, Dchang and Bamenda with several primary, secondary and tertiary educational institutions. All four universities have experienced some growth over the years not only in the increase in the number of teachers and students but, in the number of programmes and faculties/school/colleges. The University of Douala was created by presidential Decree N° 93/026 of 19 January 1993, same year with Buea, Dschang while Bamenda in 2010 but, by different presidential Decree.

With reference to Buea, Data from www.ubuea.cm, indicated that the University of Buea has eight (8) Faculties; Faculty of Arts (FA), Faculty of Education (FED), Faculty of Social and Management Sciences (FSMS), Faculty of Science (FS), Faculty of Engineering (FET), Faculty of Health Sciences (FHS), Faculty of Agriculture and Veterinary Medicine (FAVM), Faculty of Law and Political Science (FLP), and three (3) Schools: Advanced school of Translators and Interpreters (ASTI), College of Technology (COT), Higher Technical Teacher Training College (HTTTC) Kumba. Generally, in recent times, education has become one of the major activities in Buea with several primary, secondary and tertiary educational institutions. With key interest in tertiary institutions, there are thirty-three (33) in number in South West Region, wherein, there is one (01) State University, two (02) confessional and thirty (30) Lay Private Universities in the South West Region.

Furthermore, data from uniba-edu.cm, indicated that, University of Bamenda is made up of Faculty of Arts (FA), Faculty of Education (FED), Faculty of Social and Management Sciences (FSMS), Faculty of Science (FS), Faculty of Health Sciences (FHS), The Higher Institute of Commerce and Management, The Higher Institute of Transport and Logistics, Faculty of Law and Political Science (FLP), College of Technology (COT), Agriculture, Higher Teacher Training College (HTTC), Higher Technical Teachers' Training College (HTTTC), and the National Higher Polytechnic Institute (NAHPI, School of Engineering). There are twenty-two (22) Higher Institutions in the NorthWest Region made up of one public, three confessional and eighteen lay privates.

Geographically, the area (Northwest) experiences the Tropical climate type with two main seasons; rainy and dry, low relative humidity and mean annual temperature and rainfall of about 20.80C and 2140mm, respectively. Bambili lies on 5.9830N and 10.250E and is elevated at about 1558m ASL. The major vegetation type is the tropical savannah characterised by fewer trees and tall vegetation which sometimes reaches a height of 4m.

Again, the university of Douala while located in one of the largest cities in the country called Douala, it has a number of campus facilities located in different parts of the nation the university offers full time undergraduate and postgraduate degree programs including fields such as sciences and social sciences, some of the university's faculties include; faculty of legal and political science, faculty of economics and applied management. Engineering, Industrial Engineering, Medicine and Pharmacy, Arts, Management and Social Science, Anthropology, Human Resource Management, English, History, Music, Business Administration Science & Technology Computer Science, Mathematics, Physics, Biochemistry Law. The University of Douala has six locations in different neighborhoods of the city of Douala: Campus Bassa, Campus Ndogbong, Campus Akwa (Ecole doctorale), Nkongsamba, Nkongsamba, Yabassi, and Logbessou (construction started in 2011).

Geographically, In the Littoral region, the University of Douala was chosen for the study. Douala lies on 4.05110N and 9.76790E and about 13m ASL. It is the economic headquarters of Cameroon and the administrative headquarters of the Littoral Region. Douala falls within the confines of one of the four divisions of the region, namely the Wouri division. The city lies on the estuary of river Wouri and the climate type is the Guinea type with high relative humidity (about 79.8%), high temperatures (about 26.20C) and high rainfall amounts (about 3702mm) throughout the year.

Finally, the University of Dschang while is about 425 kilometers Northwest of Yaoundé, it has its roots in three agricultural training schools, and evolved from an agricultural institution to a university in 1993. Agriculture Animal production Soil science, Agricultural extension and rural sociology, Medicine, and Pharmacy, Medicine, Pharmacy Arts, Management and Social Science, Finance and Accounting, Economics Political Science, Science and Technology Biochemistry, Geology, Chemistry Biomedical Science, Law. Below is map showing the location of the four study areas (Bamenda, Dschang, Buea and Douala). These four Universities have a total of over 2101 academic staff with University of Douala having the highest among them and Bamenda the lowest.

Population of Study

Kenton (2020) defined population in statistics as an entire pool from which a statistical sample is drawn. Furthermore, a population is an aggregate observation of subjects grouped together by a common feature Kothari (2004). In the context of the study, the population comprised of students in the University of Buea, and Bamenda, in the South West and North West Regions of Cameroon respectively. At the time of the study, statistics were gathered from the Ministry of Higher Education, with the recent statistics available is that for 2021. Therefore, this study made use of it. Below is the statistics on the number of students in the four universities by gender.

Table 1 The Distribution of Students in Different Faculties/Institutions in Buea University

Faculties/Institutions	Frequency
Advanced School of Translators and Interpreters (ASTI)	378
College of Technology (COLTECH)	829
Faculty of Agriculture and Veterinary medicine (FARMV)	898
Faculty of Arts (FA)	1744
Faculty of Education	4682
Faculty of Engineering and Technology	1067
Faculty of health science	2029
Faculty of Law and Political Science	5372
Faculty of Science	5078
Faculty of Social and Management Science	10616
Higher Technical Teacher Training College	2194
Total	34887

Source: "Student's Admissions Records" May 20, 2024.

Statistics for university of Buea showed that Faculty of social and management science has the highest number of students while Advanced school of translators and interpreters (ASTI) has the least number of students, followed by College of Technology (COLTECH) and Faculty of Agriculture and Veterinary medicine (FARMV).

Table 2 The Distribution of Students in Different Faculties/Institutions in Bamenda University

Faculty/Institutions	Frequency
College of Technology	897
Faculty of Arts	1829
Faculty of Economics and Management	1233
Faculty of Education	533
Faculty of Health Sciences	1083
Faculty of law and political Science	1519
Faculty of Science	2369
Higher institute of Commerce and Management	920
Higher Teachers Training College	1789
Higher Technical Teachers Training College	1358
Higher Institute of Transport and Logistics	559
National Higher Polytechnic Institute.	606
Total	14695

Source: "Student's Admissions Records" May 20, 2024.

Statistics for university of Bamenda showed that Faculty of science has the highest number of students although the gap is not wide when compared to faculty of arts, law and political Science, Higher Technical Teachers Training College and Higher Teachers Training College while Faculty of Education has the least number of students.

Target Population of Study

Creswell (2009) defined target population is a group which the researcher is interested in gaining information upon which generalization and conclusions can be drawn subsequently. In this study, the target population of this study was made up of students from five faculties that is; Faculty of science, Faculty of Education, Faculty of Arts, Faculty of Health Sciences, Faculty of Agriculture and Veterinary Medicine, College of Technology, selected from the University of Buea and Bamenda. The statistics is presented on the table below.

Table 3 Target Population of the Study

University	Classical faculties	Students
University of Buea	College of Technology (COLTECH)	829
	Faculty of Agriculture and Veterinary medicine (FARMV)	898
	Faculty of Arts (FA)	1744
	Faculty of Education	4682
	Faculty of Health Science	2029
University of Bamenda	Faculty of Arts	1829
	Faculty of Science	2069
	College of Technology	897
	Faculty of Education	583
	Faculty of Health Sciences	1083
Total		16,643

Source: "Student's Admissions Records" May 20, 2024.

Statistics from the table of target population showed that there are **16,643** students from the faculties/schools/colleges of interest from the two universities

Accessible Population

Accessible population is defined as the population to which the researcher has reasonable access (Creswel, 2009). Larakas (2008) defined accessible population as the subset of the target population and the study population. Asiamah (2017) defined accessible population as those individuals, groups and events that are to be studied. In the context of the study, amongst the 16,643 students, 14,635 students are undergraduate students. From these undergraduate students, students from Curriculum Studies and Teaching, Special Education and Educational Psychology, Chemistry, Biochemistry, History, Medicine, Bilingual Letters, Agriculture and Veterinary Medicine and College of Technology made up the accessible population of the study.

Table 4 Accessible Population of the Study

Programmes	Total number of undergraduates
Curriculum Studies and Teaching	664
Special Education	454
Educational Psychology	519
Chemistry	334
Biochemistry	376
Geology	201
Medicine	198
Bilingual letters	876
History	478
Agronomy	298
Technology	176
Total	4,574

Source: "Student's Admissions Records" May 20, 2024.

Statistics from 11 accessible programmes showed that there 4,574 students.

Sample and Sampling Technique

Sample

An ideal sample for any study should be large enough for adequate representation of the population of the study and for generalization of findings (Best & Kahn, 2006). A sample is the subset of individuals from a larger population. For the calculation of a single population proportion, the sample size is calculated using the Cochran formula. The formula is used because the researchers did not have prior information on the total number of students in the study area. The Cochran

formula: $(n = z^2pq/e^2)$ can be used to determine an appropriate sample size (n) for an estimated proportion (P) of the attribute present in the sample, a given degree of precision (e), and desired level of confidence interval (CI). For this study, we assumed a proportion (P) of 50% for undergraduate students, 95% confidence interval ($Z = 1.96$), and a marginal error (d) of 5%. By substituting these values in the above formula $[(1.96)^2(0.50)(1-0.05)/(0.05)^2]$, and considering a non-response rate of 10%, the estimated minimum sample size was 500 undergraduate students was computed. Using the same formula, we equally we equally assumed a prevalence (P) of 50% for stunting, 95% confidence interval ($Z = 1.96$), and a marginal error (d) of 5%. By substituting these values in the above formula $[(1.96)^2(0.50)(1-0.05)/(0.05)^2]$, and considering a non-response rate of 10%, the estimated minimum sample size was 500.

Table below presents the number of participants per category of key informants who will participate in the IDIs. A purposive sample of 4 key informants (2 guidance counsellors and 2 chaplain) will be enrolled for individual interviews from among in the study area.

Categories of participants, sample size, and number of IDIs for the study.

Table 5 Categories of participants, sample size, and number of IDIs for the study

Source of Data	University of Buea	University of Bamenda	Total number of IDIs
	N	N	N
Pastors from one church in student's milieu in Buea and Bamenda	1	1	2
Guidance counsellors (one each from Faculty of health sciences)	1	1	2
Student representatives (one each from Faculty of health sciences)	1	1	2

Table 6 Sample Frame by Programme

Programmes	Total number of undergraduates	Sample
Curriculum Studies and Teaching	664	70
Special Education	454	50
Educational Psychology	519	50
Chemistry	334	52
Biochemistry	376	38
Geology	201	31
Medicine	198	31
Bilingual letters	876	65
History	478	50
Agronomy	298	46
Technology	176	27
Total	4,574	500

n =number; s =sample

Thus, out of the 500 students making the sample size, 399 came from Level 400 University of Buea students, 101 level 400 from University of Bamenda students.

Treatment of Data

Responses from the closed ended response options were scored using the response format and weighting scale below.

Table 7 Response Format and Weighting Scale

Type of Statement	Response Options and Associated Scores			
	Strongly Agree (SA)	Agree (A)	Disagree (DA)	Strongly Disagree (SDA)
Positive statement	1	3	2	1
Negative statement	1	2	3	4

Results on table 9 showed that, any respondent to a positive statement who ticked Strongly Agree (SA) scored 4 points for that item. Agree (A) scored 3 points, disagreed (DA) scored 2 points, while Strongly Disagreed (SDA) scored 1 point. For negative statements, the scoring guide was reversed, with Strongly Agree (SA) having the score 1 point, Agree (A) – 2 points, Disagree (DA) – 3 points and strongly Disagree (SDA) having the score 4 points.

The total score of each respondent per variable was computed and converted on 20. Each score was approximated to the nearest whole number and impacted in the data sheet see data sheet in appendix

Demographic Data

Table 8 Age of Respondents

Age Range	Frequency	Percentage
20-25yrs	216	44.3
16-20yrs	156	31.0
25-30yrs	66	13.5
Missing Data	43	8.8
30yrs	7	1.4
Total	488	100.0

Results on table 10 showed that the sample of respondents was mostly students of age within 16 and 25yrs. Their cumulative percentage is 75.3% with more of them falling within the age range 20 to 25yrs (44.3%). Those within the range 25 to 30yrs represent 13.5% of the sample. There was a missing data of 8.8% while those above 30yrs represent 1.4% of the sample.

Table 9 Gender of Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	259	53.1
Male	202	41.4
Missing Data	27	5.5
Total	488	100.0

Results on table 11 show that the sample was dominated with more females (53.1%) than males (41.4%). There was a missing data of 5.5%.

Table 10 Marital Status

Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	409	83.8
Married	68	13.9
Missing Data	21	4.3
Total	488	100.0

Results on table 12 showed that the sample was dominated by singles (83.8%) as against those who are married (13.9%), missing data was 4.3%.

Table 11 University Attending

University	Frequency	Percentage
Buea	387	79.3
Bamenda	97	19.9
Missing Data	4	0.8
Total	488	100.0

Results on table 13 showed that most of the respondents were from the University of Buea (79.3%) as against 19.9% for University of Bamenda. There was missing data of 0.8%.

Sampling Techniques

Sampling is defined as the process of selecting a smaller group of participants to essentially communicate what the larger population might provide. Also, sampling is a technique of selecting individual members or a subset of the population to make statistical inferences from them and estimate the characteristics of the whole population (Best & Kahn, 2006). Sampling is the process of selecting a smaller group of participants to essentially communicate what the larger population might provide. In the context of the study, the simple random, purposive, and convenient sampling techniques will be adopted for the study.

The simple random sampling technique was used in selecting the two Universities out of the eight state Universities in Cameroon. To do this, the names of all eleven universities were written on separate pieces of papers, folded and placed in a basket. After this, the fold papers were then reshuffled and the researcher hand pick papers and the name of the university written on it was chosen for the study. By this, every university had equal chance of being selected for the study.

Thereafter, purposive sampling technique was applied whereby a few faculties/schools/colleges of the two state universities randomly chosen was selected for the study. This technique was used in order to purposely sample programmes that had a good number students alongside few programmes that do not have many students thereby, striving for a balance. The purposive sampling methods will also be used to select counselors and chaplains that will be interviewed

Instruments of Data Collection

Questionnaire and structured interview guide will be the instruments adopted for the interview of chaplains and guidance counselors. The reason for using questionnaire on students was because it gave room for more questions to be asked and to sample a large number of them as it was the case in the study. On the other hand, the reasons for using the semi-structured interview guide for academic staff and parents was because first, only a few questions were designed for them to elaborately explained themselves by providing those responses that students could not really provide accurate responses to. Second, the instrument was dominant with open ended questions and third, only a small number of them were sample for the study as this fit the characteristics of an interview guide.

Description of the Questionnaire

McLeod (2018) defined a questionnaire as a research instrument consisting of a series of questions for the purpose of gathering information from the respondents. It is generally, a series of written questions for which the respondents have to provide the answers. A questionnaire was adopted for the study because it permits the researcher to collect data from a large number of individuals.

Structurally, the questionnaire is design into section A, B, C, D and E. The first part (section A) consists of a brief consent form that state; who the researcher is, the purpose of the study, and stating the reason why the participants are important for the study. In this first part, there is demographic data such; such as name of university, gender, age, socio-economic status, marital status of parents, family structure, frequent conflict at home between parents and siblings, number of siblings and highest level of parent education.

The second part of the questionnaire consisted of items relating to the constructs/specific objectives of the study. In this second part, there is a section 'B' which consists of final test items on empathy, (Items 1-10). Section 'C' consist of test items on cooperation (Items 11-20). Section 'D' also consist of test items on volunteering (Items 21-30). Section 'E' measures help (Items 31-40) and "F" measures self-esteem. In total, the questionnaire has 50 closed ended items rated using the four-point likert scale (Strong Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree).

Table12 Weighted Values for Response Options

Test items	Response options			
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Positively worded items	4	3	2	1
Negatively worded items	1	2	3	4

Descriptive of Interview

This is a conversation with the purpose to gather in-depth information from respondents of the subject matter. Creswell (2012) defined an interview as a face-to-face conversation between a researcher and a participant involving a transfer of information to the interviewer. The interview guide was made for few female adolescent students to expatiate on the implication and relevance of family prosocial behaviours on their self-esteem.

Structurally, the interview guide also organised into two main parts. The first part consists of a brief consent form that state; who the researcher is, the purpose of the study, and stating the reason why the participants are important for the study. In this first part, there is section 'A' which captures respondent's demographic data such; university, gender, age, socio-economic status, marital status of parents, family structure, frequent conflict at home between parents and siblings, number of siblings and highest level of parent education. The second part that is section 'B' consists of six 12 (12) open ended questions related to the objectives of the study. That is each research question had three open ended questions.

Validation of Instruments

Validity and reliability are two important concepts in the acceptability of the use of an instrument for research purposes (Amin, 2005). Validity is the accuracy and meaningfulness of inferences, which is based on the research results. It is a degree to which results obtained from the analysis of the data actually represented the phenomenon under study. Also, validity is concerned with the extent to which the instrument measures what it was supposed or intended to measure. In this study, three forms of validity were addressed with the objective to ensure the instruments measured what they intended to measure, and the findings of the study valid and reliable for generalisation. Below is how the validity of the instruments was ascertained.

Validity of Instruments

Content Validity

Content validity focused on the extent to which the content of the instrument corresponded to the concepts/ sub-variables of the study. To ensure that the content validity of the instruments was attained, the instruments were designed with the aid of related literature reviewed for the study. This was to ensure that the test items on the instrument correspond to the indicators of the variables under the study and subject matter. Furthermore, after the construction of the instrument, sample copies were submitted to the two supervisors for examination, appraisal and further scrutiny of the test items. All corrections made were taken into consideration and effected as indicated by the supervisors.

Construct Validity

Frost (2019) defined construct validity as the soundness of inferences that one draw from test scores and other measurements. Specifically, construct validity addresses whether a test measures the intended construct. In the context of the study and after the test items were generated making use of the related literature, the copies of the interview guide, and questionnaire were given to other lecturers and the statistician. The purpose for this is to ensure that the test items are valid for the study and are true characteristics or attributes of the variables to ascertain the validity of the findings.

The corrections made by different category of persons were taken into consideration and from the responses; the construct validity index (CVI) for each of the test items was calculated. This was done by dividing the number of time that an item was declared valid by the total number of persons who reviewed the instrument. During this process, the test items that score validity index of less than 0.7 which is the recommended threshold were either modified or discarded.

$$\text{Formula for CVI} = \frac{\text{Number of judges that declared an item valid}}{\text{Total number of judges}}$$

Face Validity

Finally, face validity of the instruments was also be taken into consideration. This is to ensure that the instruments with it test items or questions are not valid for the study but, the entire instruments is reader friendly, instructions well outline and the language is simple for every respondents to quickly understand despite differences in level of education.

Reliability of the Instruments

According to Joppe (2000), reliability is defined as the extent to which results are consistent over time and an accurate representation of the total population under study and if the results of a study can be reproduced under a similar methodology, then the research instrument is considered to be reliable. In most cases the reliability of research instruments concerns the extent to which the instrument yields the same result or repeated trials. That is the degree to which the instrument measures what was intended to be measured (Lufumbi, 2010).

Reliability measures the extent to which the respondents are consistent and objective in their responses. Reliability analysis is an important indicator that determines a good quantitative research instrument. Therefore, to ensure that the instruments are reliable for the study, a pilot study has to be carried out on 20 students. Data collected will tested using the Cronbach Alpha test for each of the construct. Furthermore, a detail item-by-item statistics will be computed so that one could clearly see the reliability coefficient value for each item. With this additional step, it becomes easier to identify items which are problematic based on their coefficient value. The Cronbach Alpha test was preferable for the study because it measures the internal consistency of the participant responses without the research going to the field twice.

Using this test, a Coefficient value of 0.7 and above will imply that the respondents are objective and consistent in their responses meanwhile a coefficient value of less than 0.7 will imply that some of the test items or all are problematic. Below is a classification table of Cronbach Alpha coefficient for the acceptability of a quantitative instrument.

Table 13 Classification of Cronbach Alpha Coefficient(r)

No	Cronbach Alpha Coefficient(r)	Judgment
1	More than 0.9	Excellent
2	0.80-0.90	Good
3	0.70-0.79	Acceptable
4	0.6-0.69	Questionable
5	0.5-0.59	Poor
6	Less than 0.59	Unacceptable

Source: Khairul, Ismail, and Saleh, (2018)

The normal range of the coefficient alpha values is between 0.00 and +1; the higher the value, the better the internal consistency and low Alpha is considered as problematic.

On the other hand, qualitatively, reliability for the interview guide was ensured on the basis of need analysis. Needs analysis is a technique in collecting and accessing information relevant to course design. In the needs analysis, the interview is one of the methods and it involves asking in-depth questions using a structured or semi-structured guide to better understand the individual's points of view. A pilot test for an interview is an important and useful process in conducting qualitative

research as part of the study entails for, its findings might indicate that some improvements needed for the major study.

Validity and reliability of the qualitative data interview guide will depend on the researcher's expectations in the interview session with head teachers and community leaders. In conducting the interview, the researcher will play an important role to ensure that interviewees and participants understand the questions asked and at the same time the researcher will manage to get the data for the research questions. Therefore, piloting for an interview is an integral part and beneficial in the process of conducting qualitative research as it highlights the improvisation to the major study. A pilot test is conducted in any research to ensure that validity of the instruments is achieved (Majid et al, 2017). A pilot test of the interview guide was aimed at detecting any possible errors at the early stage of research which may require adjustments and adding value and credibility into the research.

In as much as there is a fixed sample in establishing the reliability for qualitative instruments, in the study, 5 of the students will be used. Thus, adequate comprehension and responses from the head teachers and community leader implies that the questions on the interview guide are reliable.

Administration of Instruments

The data for the study is collected using the face-to-face and electronic methods, that is; direct delivery method and online administration. The use of both methods is to enable the researcher collect data even from participants from a far but are within the accessible population of the study. Concerning the face-to-face method, the questionnaire will be administered to the students in their schools during their free period. Furthermore, the link of the questionnaire will be sent online through WhatsApp groups of the students. This will be done with the help of some students to share the link to their different WhatsApp groups.

As for the interview guide, two approaches will be used and the participants have to decide on the method that is most appropriate for them. These two methods are; oral and written. For participants that prefer oral method, the questions will be read to them and the responses recorded using a phone or a tape recorder. For participants that will prefer the written method, the interview guide will be presented to them with enough space provided for each question so that they can write down their responses. All field data (primary) will be collected within one month duration.

Method for Data Analysis

The qualitative and quantitative methods will be used in analyzing the data for the study.

Data Entry and Clean –Up

The data that will be collected for the study will be key using EpiData version 3.1 (EpiData Association, Odense Denmark, 2008) whereby, the questionnaire collected from the field will be coded with numbers. The purpose for coding the answer questionnaire during data entering is because in case of any error on the data base, the questionnaire can be easily traced using the assigned code from the database. The EpiData was chosen for the data entering because it is very fast, friendly and reliable and, the template can be customised to eliminate possible errors that could occur during data entering.

Furthermore, after all the data must have been key in, advanced data cleaning process with the aid of SPSS version 25 will be done using the exploratory statistics is an integrated part of data clean-up. By so doing, variables will be explored to identify questionable entries, inconsistency in responses, missing values/systems and outliers. During this stage, the fate of the missing system will also be defined depending on the statistical requirements. Frequency analysis will also be computed for categorical variables as to identify invalid entries and missing values. Box plotting techniques will equally be used to ensure efficient cleaning of the data because it demarcates outliers on a graph and their exact position in the data base such that they can easily be traced and verified.

Analysis of Quantitative Data

After the data is thoroughly checked for possible errors, the quantitative data will be analyzed using the descriptive and inferential statistical tools. The descriptive statistical tools to be used are frequency count, percentages mean, standard deviation and multiple responses set which aimed at calculating the summary of findings for each variable where applicable. The hypotheses of study will be tested using a Pearson test. This test is going to use because the data for the variables will be assumed to be approximately normally distributed which will be tested using the Komogorov test. Checking for normality assumption is very important to know the exact test(s) that is/are more suitable for the verification of hypotheses and to avoid faulty generalizations which could lead to committing the type 1 or type 2 hypothesis errors.

Analysis of Qualitative Data

On the other, the qualitative data to be derived from the semi-structured interview guide will be analyzed using the thematic analysis approach with the aid of themes, groundings/frequency and quotations. Themes are umbrella words which capture the main idea of the participants' statements. On the other hand, groundings also call frequency represent the number of times that a particular theme/concept surface from the direct statements of the participants. However, it should be noted that in the context of thematic analysis, a theme with a grounding of one is equally important like a theme with a grounding of more than one.

Finally, findings will be presented using frequency distribution tables and thematic tables with all inferential statistics presented at 95% level of confidence interval with alpha set at 0.05 levels, accepting 5% margin of error.

Decision Rule for Testing Hypotheses

The null hypothesis is rejected if the computed P-value is $>$, error margin of 5% and

The alternative hypothesis is accepted if the computed P-value is $<$, error margin of 5%

Effect Size

The numerical value for the effect size, r_p ranges between -1 and +1 and determines the extent to which the predictors are associated to the criterion. The magnitudes of the effect sizes are; $r_p = 0$ implies no association (effect size); $r_p = < 0.20$ implies extremely low association (effect size); $r_p = 0.20 - 0.39$ implies low association (effect size); $r_s = 0.40 - 0.59$ implies moderate association (effect size); $r_s = 0.60 - 0.79$ implies high association (effect size); $r_s = 0.80 - 0.99$ implies extremely high association (effect size) and 1.00 a perfect association/effect.

Statistical Formula

$$\text{Cronbach Alpha } \alpha = \frac{k}{k-1} \left[1 - \frac{\sum \text{Items variances}}{\text{Scale variance}} \right]$$

Where α = Cronbach Alpha

K= number of items

$$\text{Percentage}(\%) = \frac{\text{Frequencycount } (n)}{\text{Totalnumberofpersons } (N)} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

$$\text{Mean} = \frac{\sum fx}{\sum f}$$

Where \sum =Summation, f = frequency and x =value

Spearman's Rho

$$1 - \frac{6 \sum D^2}{N(N^2-1)}$$

Where;

Σ =Summation

D=difference in rank

N=Number of observations

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient

Raw Score method

$$\frac{n(\epsilon xy) - (\epsilon x)(\epsilon y)}{\sqrt{[n(\epsilon x^2) - (\epsilon x)^2][n(\epsilon y^2) - n(\epsilon y)^2]}}$$

Where;

Σ =Summation

Y=Values corresponding to the independent variable

X=Values corresponding to the dependent variable

Kolmogorov One Sample Test= D (KS)= Maximum\Fo(x)-Fr (X)|

Where =

Fo(x)= Observed cumulative frequency of a random sample of n observations and

$$F_o(x) = \frac{k}{n} = \text{No. of observations} \leq X / (\text{Total no. of observations})$$

Fr (X)= The theoretical frequency distribution.

Ethical Considerations

Acting ethically in research ensures that the subjects are treated with respect and sensitivity beyond what the law may require. Administrative approval to carry out this study will be obtained from the Faculty of Education of the University of Buea through the Dean in charge of research. Furthermore, authorisation will also be requested from each university that will be visited. Verbal consent of each category of participants will be duly sought. Participants who will take part will be verbally appreciated but those who will not be interested will not be convince in any way to participate in the study. The participants will also give assurance that their responses will be treated with utmost confidentiality.

Furthermore, to the participants, the significance and helpfulness of the study will be justifying why it was important for them to take part in the study. In this line, the researcher made sure the participants are adequately aware of the information needed from them, why the information is needed from them, and how the data will be treated. On the researcher's part, ethical concerns consisted of avoiding bias, using appropriate research methods to validate the data collection instruments, and reporting findings correctly without falsifying them. Finally, other ethical issues have to do with aspects such as negotiation, informed consent, voluntary participation, researcher relationship and the survey research design using the exploratory method was adopted for the study.

The target population of the study comprised of students in some faculties/school/colleges in four state universities namely; university of Buea and university of Bamenda. The sample size of the study consisted of 500 students. The participants are sample using simple random sampling and purposive sampling. Questionnaire and, interview guide are the instruments adopted for the study. This chapter equally saw the techniques used to ensure the validity and reliability of the instruments and method of data collection. Finally, SPSS version 25 (Statistical Package for Social Science) with the aid of descriptive and inferential statistical tools are statistical techniques chosen to analyze the data. Lastly, the ethical considerations guiding the study are also explained.

4. CHAPTER FOUR

PRESENTATION OF DATA AND FINDINGS

Introduction

Data collected from the field were analysed descriptively and inferentially. For descriptive statistics, frequencies, percentages and thematic analysis were used, while for inferential statistics, the Pearson Correlation Coefficient Product Moment (PCCPM) and the Multiple Regression Analyses tests were used to test the hypotheses.

Table 14 Strategy used to cope with Psychosocial Problems

Strategy	Frequency	Percentage
Guidance and Counselling	264	54.1

Results on table 14 showed that the most used coping strategy is guidance and counselling (54.1%) of the participant

Figure 4 Use of coping strategies by students

From the 264 Students who used guidance and counselling, graded how effective it was for them on a scale of 1-10. Scores 8-10 were considered very effective, 5-7 were considered moderately effective and 1-5 were considered mildly effective. Below are the results;

Table15 Effectiveness of the use of guidance counselling

Strategy	Very effective	Moderately effective	Mildly effective	Total	%
Guidance and Counselling	200	34	30	264	100.0

Results on table 4.8 show that of 264 students who used guidance and counselling 75.5 % found it very effective for them, 12.8% found it moderately effective and 11.7% found it mildly effective.

Figure 5 Number students who used guidance and counselling and how effective they found it

From the 68 Students who peer support, graded how effective it was for them on a scale of 1-10. Scores 8-10 were considered very effective, 5-7 were considered moderately effective and 1-5 were considered mildly effective. Below are the results;

Research Question: What are the effects of counselling services in the management of psychosocial problems?

Table 19 Organisation of Responses into Major and Sub Themes Relating to the Effects of Counselling Services in Managing Psycho-social Problems

Major themes	Sub themes
-Emotional well-being	-Modifies my emotions to be more positive
	-Improves on my ability to think positively
	-General improvement of self-esteem
	-Corrects my moods, self-esteem and resilience
	-Improves self-confidence
	-Enables one to sleep well
	-Reduces stress
	-Reduces depression and anxiety
-Problems solving skills	-Provides temporal solution
	-Resolves conflicts
	-Calms situations and provides the way forward
	-Sharing your problems with a counsellors gives you some relief
	-Makes good and informed decisions
	-Manages stress properly
-General Improvement in mental health	-Improves reasoning
	-Heals physical, social and mental state of an individual
	-Overcomes mental stress
	-Provides consciousness to my actions
-Improved confidence	-Enables one to handle psychosocial problems
	-Enables the students to see value in himself
	-Builds moral attitudes to act positively
	-Builds confidence in handling school life and social challenges
	-Enables the student to be more conscious of his actions
-Improved interpersonal relationships	-Creates awareness for a better understanding of the environment to avoid problems with others
	-Provides guidance on how to solve or avoid problems with others
	-Corrects your association with others
	-Improves communication with others
-High academic performance	-Able to reason well and answer questions
	-Able to solve mathematical problems individually
	-Able to pass my exams with good grades
	-Able to share good ideas with colleagues

Results on table 19 show that the response registered on the open-ended item of the questionnaire were first organised in sub themes and further grouped into major themes. From table 19 the effects of counselling service are emotional wellbeing, improved problem-solving skills, general improvement in mental health, improved confidence, improved interpersonal relations and a high academic performance.

Responses from the interview conducted on (2) Guidance Counsellors in University of Buea and University of Bamenda in relation to response on Research Questions.

Table 20 The Impressions of Students on Psychosocial problems

From Guidance Counsellor	From Students' Representatives	From Sports and Culture Coordinator	From Spiritual Counsellors
-Difficulties students face as students	-Problems from homes, campus and peers	-The various difficulties people go through in handling life situations	-They are psycho-emotional problems
Social and psychological problems of students	-The problems vary from student to student	-Problems of youths, disruptive situations in life from homes and the society	-Mental and social problems
-Emotional problems	-Major problems faced by students with current trends in life such as fashion, social media and competition	They are varied and relate to students' background	-Family, financial and other related school problems
-Family and financial problems	-Stress encountered by students		-The cycle of problems that greatly affect students

The results on table 20 above show some differences in their impressions on what students' psychosocial problems are. However, they are converged on the facts that:

They are problems, difficulties and challenges faced by students in their lives due to social, mental and home situations.

Table 21 The Rate of Reception of Students in Your Service, Services Rendered and Example

From Guidance Counsellor	From Students' Representatives	From Sports and Culture Coordinator	From Spiritual Counsellors
-The rate is average compared to our expectations	-We receive a few students (about 10 daily) due to lack of sponsorship	-Rate of reception is about 10%	-We receive 4 to 6 students during church service
-Some come intermittently when faced with serious problems	-They come in once in a while	-We receive students with psychosocial problems	-We receive students going through psychological torments
-We provide a platform where worries are shared and we help reduce the burden they carry	-Some problems are: have low esteem because they don't dress like others, home problems, negative peer influence	-Examples: When they have to face relatives/parents with poor academic performance	-We prescribe to them spiritual help
-We make follow up to reduce the stress they carry		-Difficulties with roommates, premarital sex	-We connect them to God
		-Students come for orientation on mentor-mentee relationship	-Stress due to exams, we pray for them and they overcome the stress
		They are relieved after sporting activities	

Results on table 21 show that, all the services receive students on psycho-social problems with the counselling service receiving most. The encounters in each of these services are for particular reasons, because spiritual counselling has specific examples of problems they handle. So is it for physical and sports counselling service, peers, etc. Each handles a specific area to relieve psycho-social crises.

Table 22 Responses on Effectiveness of the various services on managing students' psychosocial problems and the barriers they face

From Guidance Counsellor	From Students' Representatives	From Sports and Culture Coordinator	From Spiritual Counsellors
-Our services are recommended to students by students due to their effectiveness -Effectiveness is shown by the fact that the students manage their problems on their own <u>Barriers</u> -The use is limited due to lack of sensitisation -Lack of knowledge about our service	-Very effective and powerful tool in redressing psychosocial problems -Most students recover faster from psychosocial problems if their peer stand with them Negative: Some support may lead to depressions and more problems <u>Barriers:</u> -Bad advices from peers -Limited resources -Lack of knowledge	-Not as much effective -It has a limited sphere of influence -It must be supported by other services to make it effective <u>Barriers:</u> -Lack of motivation of students to seek redress from this service -Lack of sufficient sports infrastructure -This service though helpful, it is informal in redressing psychosocial problems.	-Very effective -After counselling, the students regain confidence and courage -They persevere and feel relieved -The remarks from students have been very positive <u>Barriers:</u> -Some students shy away -Some are not informed of the role of spiritual counselling

Table 22 above shows that all the services are very effective in handling psychosocial problems except for sports and cultural service which is not as much effective due to the fact that it has to get support from other services. The major barrier that cuts across all the services is that of lack of knowledge by students regarding their roles in redressing psychosocial problems.

Table 23 Responses on whether or not students make use of other services in and out of the University and which ones are more effective

From Guidance Counsellor	From Students' Representatives	From Sports and Culture Coordinator	From Spiritual Counsellors
-Yes, they do -They use families, church leaders, parental assistance, friends and classmates <u>More effective services</u> - Parental assistance -Church leaders	-Yes, they do -They use religious services like Pastors and Imans, church counsellors, clubs like sports club, bible club, other associations, online counsellors, parents, NGOs incharge of psychosocial support, stress managers <u>More effective</u> -Christian leaders, bible club	-Yes, they do -Parental assistance, friends, church leaders, teachers, guidance counsellors <u>More effective</u> -Parental assistance -Church leaders	-Yes, they do -They use guidance counsellors, friends and classmates <u>More effective service</u> -They believe peers play a great role

Results on table 23 showed that all the interviewees stated that students make use of other services out of the University to manage their psychosocial problems. Each of them listed those who are

contacted and church leaders and parental assistance are cited by all the interviewees. They are also seen as the more effective in the services they render.

Table 24 Responses on Barriers faced by Students in the use of the services cited on table... and proposals for the University to improve on their psychosocial services

From Guidance Counsellor	From Students' Representatives	From Sports and Culture Coordinator	From Spiritual Counsellors
<p><u>Barriers</u> -Service providers are not always available -Breach of confidentiality -Fear of abuse and stigma -Lack of information</p> <p><u>Proposals for improvement</u> -Sensitisation campaign on campus are needed on how to manage psychosocial problems -Service providers should always make themselves available -The ethics and deontology of the counselling service should be upheld by service providers.</p>	<p><u>Barriers</u> -Fear of being stigmatised on the problem -Lack of trust by the student</p> <p><u>Proposals for improvement</u> -Many service providers be recruited to work in the university milieu -Service providers should make their doors open at all times -Students be taught on how to manage their psychosocial problems</p>	<p><u>Barriers to service users</u> -Ignorance on the part of the user -Poor peer influence -Lack of collaboration -Lack of information -Lack of interest</p> <p><u>Proposals for Improvement</u> -The service users need education on how to manage their psychosocial problems -Several service providers in different domains should be employed in the university milieu. -Bible classes be made compulsory</p>	<p><u>Barriers to service users</u> -Lack of information -Lack of knowledge on how to meet the service providers</p> <p><u>Proposals for Improvement</u> -Education of the students on how to use the services is very vital</p>

Results on table 24 showed that the major barrier on the use of psychosocial services is lack of information. The major proposals for improvement are: sensitisation campaigns and the recruitment of several service providers to work in the University.

Hypothesis Testing

The Pearson Product Moment Correlation () Coefficient Value and the regression analysis tests were used to test the hypotheses.

Hypothesis 1

Null hypothesis (Ho): Counselling services are not effective in the management of their psychosocial problems amongst University students in Cameroon.

Alternative hypothesis (Ha): Counselling services are effective in the management of their psychosocial problems amongst University students in Cameroon.

Table 28 Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Value from SPSS Analyses on Guidance Counselling Services and Management of Psychosocial Problems

Variables	N	df	Σx	Σx^2	Σxy	r_{xy}	$r_{xy-Crit}$
			Σy	Σy^2		comp	
Counselling services			7708	87032	63680		
Management of psychosocial problems	490	488				0.703**	0.103
			4264	43511			

P=0.01 is significant at one end

Verification of Hypothesis

At a confidence level of 99% for a one tailed hypothesis, the computed Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient computed value (r_{xy}) is 0.703 for degree of freedom 488 and its correspondent table value $r_{xy-crit}$ (0.103), we reject the null hypothesis following the decision rule.

Inference made leads us to conclude that counselling services are effective in the management of psychosocial problems amongst university students in Cameroon. The magnitude of its effectiveness was determined following the table below.

Table 29 Magnitude of Effectiveness of the Independent Variable on the Dependent Variable

Range	Magnitude	Maximum Value
0.68-1	High	1
0.34-0.67	Moderate	
0.00-0.33	Low	

Table 29 above showed that, within the range of 0.68 and 1, the magnitude is high. Between 0.34 and 0.67 it is moderate and between 0.00 to 0.33, it is low.

Since value r_{xy} - computed value (0.703) falls within the range 0.68 and 1 the level of effectiveness of counselling services on management of psychosocial problems is high. This shows that a higher utilisation of guidance counselling services is associated with better management of psychological problems.

5. DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATION

Introduction

This chapter presents the discussion of the findings of this study objective by objective by summarising how the findings are similar and different from existing literature. It continues with the contributions of the study to educational practice and psychological research. More so, it also concludes the study by highlighting the initial purpose of the study, the methods that were used, the findings that were realized, the contributions that have been made to educational practice and psychological research. Finally, it ends with the recommendations, strengths of the study and suggestions for further research.

Discussions

Research Question One: What are the effects of counselling services in the management of psychosocial problems?

Results showed that the response registered on the open-ended item of the questionnaire were first organised in sub themes and further grouped into major themes. The effects of counselling service are emotional wellbeing, improved problem-solving skills, general improvement in mental health, improved confidence, improved interpersonal relations and a high academic performance.

These results therefore show that students, after making use of the counselling services in and out of the university milieu found it effective and listed out some relevant effects they experienced after counselling services. Results show that, all the services receive students on psycho-social problems with the counselling service receiving most. The encounters in each of these services are for particular reasons, because spiritual counselling has specific examples of problems they handle. So is it for physical and sports counselling service, peers, etc. Each handles a specific area to relieve psycho-social crises. These findings are closely to a study carried out by The Reaching Out Survey (Karwig et al., 2015) which indicated that student counselling services were the most-cited college support service previously used by students in Ireland to obtain information and support for mental health and indicated that students were likely to use this service should they need mental health support in the future.

This findings are also closely related to other studies like, A study carried out in Australia by Sanders and Lehmann (2018) stressed the importance of modelling counselling rooms to enhance

an interplay between physical and spatial features such as paint colors, natural lighting, seat positioning, temperature, and clients' thoughts and feelings. These physical-spatial features have contributed to the healing process during counselling.

Also, Carpman and Grant (2016) affirm that clients' design-related needs are essential in enhancing the psycho-social, emotional and physical needs of clients. They suggest that accessories in a counselling room such as plants and objects like sculptures provide mental stimulation to clients, making the counselling room comfortable and appealing to counsellors, thereby revealing a counsellor's character and personality. A room facility where clients visit.

Also, In a study done in China, Liu, Ji, Chen, and Ye (2014) found that colors in a counselling room have spectrum effectiveness that triggers physiological processes in both the counsellor and the client to particular colors. For instance, light has been known to determine a client's perception of color, texture, and form (Ching, 2015). Furniture and

room design, especially positioning of furniture in a counselling room and the distance between furniture, create mutual understanding between the counsellor and the clients, bearing in mind their gender (Pressly and Heesacker, 2001).

From the interviews with guidance counsellors, they said counselling contributes to the student's emotional wellbeing, improved problem-solving skills, general improvement of mental health, improved confidence, improved interpersonal relationships and high academic performance. Despite these positive effects, the results of the interview with guidance counsellors show that, students are knowledgeable about psychosocial problems, even though the rate reception in counselling services is low. These findings are closely related to findings in a study carried out by The Psychological Counsellors in Higher Education Ireland (PCHEI) 2014–2015 report showed that clients (1,427) across six university-level counselling services in Ireland reported that counselling was a factor in their retention and/or progression, and reported that it helped them with their academic performance

Guidance counsellors also expressed the effectiveness of their services despite several barriers like lack of sensitisation on what their services can render. They also agreed that there are other effective service providers like parental assistance and church leaders. There were a number of proposals interviewees made for their services to be more functional.

The results showed that, all the services are very effective in handling psychosocial problems except for sports and cultural service which is not as much effective due to the fact that it has to get support from other services. The major barrier that cuts across all the services is that of lack of knowledge by students regarding their roles in redressing psychosocial problems.

Conclusion

Conclusively, from all the findings of this study, Guidance and Counselling services has the strongest positive relationship, This researcher thinks that, the training of school guidance counselors and school based spiritual services while in their professional schools is rich in managing psychosocial problems. This makes them more effective than peer support services and extra-curricular activities. This is supported by the results of the interview where respondents for peer group services and extra-curricular activities point to the fact that, other effective services in managing psycho-social problems are guidance and counseling and school based spiritual counseling. The study's results emphasize the importance of promoting healthy coping mechanisms amongst university students. By providing students with the necessary skills and support to manage psychosocial problems, universities can help foster a healthier and more productive learning environment. This study highlights the critical role of coping strategies in managing psychosocial problems amongst university students. By promoting healthy coping mechanisms and providing supportive environments, universities can help students navigate the challenges of higher education and achieve their full potential.

Suggestions for Further Research

We suggest that other studies carried out in the following domains to add more light on this domain of research and to contribute more to existing information on students' psychosocial problems and coping strategies;

A longitudinal study can be conducted to examine the long-term effects of coping strategies on psychosocial problems amongst university students.

Comparison study can be carried out to compare the effectiveness of different coping strategies (e.g., problem-focused, emotion-focused, avoidance) in managing psychosocial problems amongst university students.

More investigations on the impact of cultural differences on the effectiveness of coping strategies amongst university students from diverse cultural backgrounds.

Technology-based interventions can be carried out to examine the effectiveness of technology-based interventions (e.g., mobile apps, online counselling) in promoting coping strategies amongst university students.

Investigations can be carried out on the role of social support (e.g., family, friends, peers) in enhancing the effectiveness of coping strategies amongst university students.

Recommendations

The researcher recommends the following;

University counselling services: Universities should sensitise students on the availability of guidance and counselling services in the university that provide accessible and effective counselling services to support students in managing psychosocial problems.

Coping skills training: Universities should offer coping skills training programs to help students develop effective coping strategies.

Peer support programs: Universities should establish peer support programs to provide students with a supportive network of peers.

Faculty and staff training: Universities should provide training for faculty and staff on recognizing and responding to students' psychosocial problems.

Community-based interventions: Universities should collaborate with community-based organizations to provide students with access to additional resources and support.

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